

MINDFULNESS-BASED THEOCENTRIC COUNSELING: WHAT, WHY & HOW OF IT

By Noel Kok Hwee Chia & Madeline Wong Foong Yee

Noel KH Chia, an IACT-approved instructor, is a double board-certified in Educational Therapy and Special Education and is currently the principal therapist with the Pediatric Therapy Center, Singapore. Ms Madeline FY

Wong is a credentialed therapist in IACT-approved Dialogic-Diagnostic Arts Therapy. She is also an associate therapist/counselor with the Pediatric Therapy Center and also an educational facilitator for the NeuroLAT AI-enhanced cognitive training program in Singapore.

The world today has become more stressful than ever. Beginning with the Industrial Revolution (1760 to 1820-1840), humankind went through several more worldwide challenges including (i) the Great Depression (1929-1939) that caused a severe worldwide economic depression after a major fall in stock prices in the United States; (ii) the Global Financial Crisis or Great Recession (2008-2009) that was caused by the bursting of the housing market bubble, created by an overwhelming load of mortgage-backed securities that bundled high-risk loans; and (iii) the latest being the COVID-19 pandemic that is still ongoing globally since 2019. With the failed attempts to contain the coronavirus in Wuhan, China, the virus spread quickly to other parts of Asia and later, worldwide. On January 30, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) announced the outbreak as a public health emergency of international concern and later declared the episode as a pandemic on March 11, 2020. As of November 14, 2022, the pandemic had caused more than 635 million cases and 6.61 million confirmed deaths, making it one of the deadliest in the history of humankind.

Stress, anxiety, uncertainty, depression, sickness, and death have become the top concerns around the world, resulting in ubiquitous traumatic life events that linger repressively in our collective unconscious. More and more people are seeking help of any kind very desperately to understand the current situations, the key ones being the worldwide inflation with food and energy prices hitting record highs, the ongoing Russo-Ukrainian War since February 2014, the US-China Trade War that began on July 6, 2018, when the US imposed a 25 percent tariff on US\$34 billion of Chinese imports ... as well as natural catastrophes that have happened in diverse places throughout the world. Counseling has consequently been pushed to the forefront to help people cope with these challenges.

WHAT of Counseling

What is counseling? The Counseling Tutor (2019) provides a textbook WHAT definition of counseling as "a contracted meeting between a client and a counselor. The meeting happens at a set time, in an agreed place, for the sole benefit of the client" (para. 1). The meaning of counseling is ever evolving to meet the dynamic challenges of modern social pressures and demands that we often try to cope with at cost to our inner world. The role of counseling is defined by its aims and values, with the former (aims) "providing an environment that enables the client to work towards living in a more resourceful and personally fulfilling way" (Milne,

2003, p. 2) and the latter includes "Integrity, respect and impartiality ... are demonstrated throughout the counseling process" (Milne, 2003, p. 2). Hence, there are many different therapeutic approaches in counseling, such as rational emotive behavior therapy and mindfulness-based cognitive therapy.

In March 2010, delegates representing different organizations (e.g., American Association of State Counseling Boards, American College Counseling Association, and American Mental Health Counselors Association) from all over the United States met at the American Counseling Association (ACA) Conference in Pittsburgh and agreed on a unified definition of counseling as follows: "Counseling involves professional relationships designed to assist individuals, families, and groups toward mental health, wellness, educational and career goals" (Kaplan, Tarydas, & Gladding, 2014, p. 370; see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Model of Professional Counseling

Another definition of counseling which includes psychotherapy is provided by the British Association for Counseling and Psychotherapy (BACP) as follows: "Counseling and psychotherapy are umbrella terms that cover a range of talking therapies. They are delivered by trained practitioners who work with people over a short or long term to help them bring about effective change or enhance their wellbeing" (Smith, 2013, para. 1).

How effective is counseling in helping people cope with life's challenges? According to Mulhauser (2014), "[R]esearch evidence (see Hubble, Duncan, & Miller, 1999, for detail) about the effectiveness of counseling and psychotherapy overall is relatively unambiguous: counseling does work" (para. 2). He went on to add that "For a wide range of types

of psychological distress, both subjective client reports, and more objective measurements indicate that counseling and psychotherapy are effective, both in the short term and over longer periods" (Mulhauser, 2014, para. 2).

WHY of Theocentrism

Since time immemorial, God has always been there. God was there. God is still there. God is seen as a creator and divine being existing outside of time and space. God can mean different things to different people today. The ancients worshiped nature (also known as naturism or physiolatry) to answer many questions about what was going on around them at a time when science was virtually unknown. Hence, myths and legends are oral narratives used to explain frightening natural catastrophes such as floods and earthquakes. One example of nature worship is Animism, which is the belief that objects, places, and creatures all possess a distinct spiritual essence (Hornborg, 2006). Shintoism (also known as 'the Way of the Gods') is the other example. It is also essentially a worship of the physical world personified as gods or goddesses (see Frazer, 1926, for details). In other words, naturism refers to a wide "variety of religious, spiritual and devotional practices that focus on the worship of the nature spirits (e.g., known in Shintoism as *kamis*) considered to be behind the natural phenomena (e.g., tsunami and volcanic eruption) visible throughout nature" (Mathews & Smith, 1921, p. 305; examples are added by the authors).

With the emergence of monotheism, the belief in only one deity, an all-supreme being that is universally referred to as God, came into existence (see Cross & Livingstone, 1974, for detail). God becomes the answer to the WHY of all things and events that happened in the past, happening now and yet to happen in the future: the Answer with the capital A to the WHY question. In addition, there is a distinction between (i) exclusive monotheism, in which the one God is a singular existence, and (ii) both inclusive and pluriform monotheism, in which multiple gods or godly forms are recognized, but each is postulated as extensions of the same God (Baaren, 2022). Monotheism characterizes the traditions of Judaism, Christianity, and Islam.

In theocentrism, the focus is on the one God. Although theocentrism is a philosophical belief related to the Medieval Era (500–1500 AD), it can also be traced to even earlier times, discovered and described by Greek philosophers, such as Plato (b.428/427 or 424/423–d.348/347 BC) and Aristotle (b.384–d.322 BC). During the Theocentric Era, a person was studied in relation to God (also known as the Absolute Reality). A person is a created being by his Creator, with a divine purpose to accomplish while on earth. S/he must model life after instructions for living in their holy texts (Monotheistic religious books include Torah, The Bible, and The Quran) to be completely obedient to his/her Creator in this life and will return to his/her Creator when this life on earth ends.

In other words, theocentrism is defined as the belief that God is the center of the world and everything else in the universe is peripheral—including the central aspect of one's existence, as opposed to anthropocentrism or existentialism. This also means that everything one does in this world, every act one does to others, or toward nature finds its meaning and value in God. The goal of any activity in theocentrism is either to approach God or to obtain eternal life or salvation (through Christ Jesus as in the case of Christian theocentrism) after death on earth.

According to the principles of theocentrism, people are called to be conscious (mindful), considerate (respectful),

and charitable (altruistic) to others as well as toward their environment or nature, especially more so during these challenging times of global warming and climate change, the preservation of Mother Earth. Furthermore, this philosophy states that all people are called to be wise and discerning in every action they take, e.g., manipulating other people for selfish acts and personal purposes, and abusing nature without thinking about the consequences these damages can cause to their environment and their survival in the long run.

When the term 'theocentric' is added to the word 'counseling', the result is *theocentric counseling*. This form of counseling attempts to address challenges and difficulties that may be sourced from what is called *soul pain*, which, "in this context and within the context of this counseling practice, is referenced as a deep and complex suffering of the human spirit" (Delaney, n.p., para. 4). The soul pain can be manifested in terms of chronic dissatisfaction, unfulfillment, and vague emptiness or meaninglessness unrelated to wealth, status, position, or health status, which are often regarded negatively and as being worldly and materialistic.

In the true sense of [Christian] theocentric counseling, we have proposed our model (see Figure 2) adapted from Allen's (1953) four key biblical foundations in his best-selling book *God's Psychiatry* as follows :

Figure 2. Model of [Christian] Theocentric Counseling

1. How to think of God: This is based on the 23rd psalm of the Book of Psalms, beginning in English in the King James Version of the Bible: "The Lord is my shepherd" (also known by the incipit, "Dominus reget me" in Latin). Its universal message of simplicity focuses on trust in God who lovingly cares for every detail of our lives.
2. God's rule for living: This is based on the famous Ten Commandments recorded in the book of Exodus in the Bible (Chapter 20, Verses 1–17) and the Torah. They constitute a set of biblical principles related to ethics and worship in Judaism and Christianity as revealed to the prophet Moses at Mount Sinai and said to be inscribed by the finger of God on two tablets of stone, which were later kept in the Ark of the Covenant. It is interesting to note that similar commandments can also be found in the Quran.
3. How to talk to God: This is based on the Lord's Prayer found in the Gospel of Saint Matthew (Chapter 6, Verses 9–13). The Lord's Prayer (also called the Our Father or Pater Noster) is a central Christian prayer that Jesus taught as the way to pray. The first three of the seven petitions in the Lord's Prayer address God,

while the remaining four are related to human needs and concerns.

4. The keys to God's kingdom: This is found in the Gospel of Saint Matthew (Chapter 5, Verses 2-12). More widely known as The Beatitudes, these are the sayings attributed to Jesus, especially the eight blessings recounted by Jesus in His Sermon on the Mount as described in the Gospel of Saint Matthew, and four in His Sermon on the Plain as mentioned in the Gospel of Saint Luke, followed by four woes which mirror the blessings (see Majernik, Ponessa, & Manhardt, 2005, pp. 63-68).

HOW of Mindfulness

Mindfulness is the practice of purposely bringing one's attention to the present-moment experience without evaluation (Creswell, 2017; Kabat-Zinn, 2013) through meditation or other strategies, e.g., the 4-7-8 breathing technique (Weil, 2017), the mode deactivation method (Apsche, Bass, & DiMeo, 2010), and the Raisin Strategy (Hibberd & Usmar, 2015).

When the word 'mindfulness' is added to theocentric counseling, theocentric mindfulness comes into the picture when a person focuses on God and/or His Word. This is known as vertical theocentric mindfulness. However, horizontal theocentric mindfulness also comes into the picture when one realizes that God is omnipresent in one's environment, where other people and living things interact and coexist together.

In brief, theocentric mindfulness involves the following HOW-to tasks:

- Paying attention to the present with a focus on God and/or His Word;
- Doing one thing at a time now; and
- Refraining from anticipating the future and/or dwelling on the unchangeable past.

Conclusion

The WHAT-WHY-HOW of mindfulness-based theocentric counseling (MBTC) as discussed above directs a person's thoughts to focus on God and/or His Word as well as his/her immediate direct/indirect ecosystemic contacts (e.g., other people and objects). Gradually, trust and confidence emerge with the assurance that God will take care of everything regardless of the outcome for the good of those who love Him because such love surpasses knowledge, that a person may be filled with all the fullness of God. In Christianity, Jesus once said, "With man this is impossible, but with God, all things are possible" (see Gospel of Saint Mark, Chapter 10, Verse 27). This is when God reveals Himself as El Shaddai (God Almighty) who holds all power and all might. In essence, this is MBTC (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. The MBTC Model

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